

MODERN DAY TEACHING AND PROBLEMS IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: *This research paper aims to present innovations and advances in modern day teaching along with the problems associated with them. In this day and age, with the assist of technology particularly AI tools process of learning has been much eased. Most of the cases it seems that technology and innovation in education meet the learners needs. On the other hand, there are underlying issues to consider prior to really judge situation. The problems this paper implies are timing - to put straightforward, allocated time that the students set aside to acquire a new language or skill. The amount they have planned is not sufficient enough. In addition, side effects of the usage of technology in education. Moreover, methodology that the teacher would like to implement may be inadequate due to some factors. Furthermore, the experience of the teacher. What is more, rapid changes in language structure can bring about frustration in learners.*

This paper provides detailed data regarding the drawbacks mentioned above and possible solutions. Also conclusion part summarizes all the key factors and the reference part shows the used materials to justify the perspectives provided in this article.

Introduction

At the current time request for learning languages is immense as English is the dominant lingua franca of the world. Old and young at the same time desire to master the languages because they open wide doors and abundant chances for people. For example, it may be career or higher education opportunities. No matter what the reason is languages especially English are a must-learn language for people of different colors. Thanks to technology learning has become fun and effortless. Everyone is enjoying with studies and playing different educational games to ace their skills. There are, however, drawbacks in education related to the present-day teaching.

1.1 Problem with timing

Owing to the extra work overload and outside pressure, most individuals are reluctant to spend enough time on language acquisition and thus they want to learn a language intensively. It is not a secret that most courses both online and traditional face-to-face classes around the world offer intensive language courses. From my perspective, I do believe that in this process students just suffer themselves putting even more pressure on themselves. As Noam Chomsky (1986) claims there is a universal grammar and language acquisition goes through like babies learn the language. That is why they may blindly learn a language without fully understanding or developing their language competence. Another reason for that language can not be mastered in a short amount of time because in a brief amount of time understanding some of the basics may occur yet implementing the knowledge by completely comprehending it is impossible. As Krashen (1985) stresses in his comprehensible input hypothesis, language learning and implementing happens when the materials are fully digested and understood comprehensively by the learner and obviously it takes ample time. Role of consciousness in input processing is significant and

degree of “noticing” in language acquisition is a key (Bialystok 1978). Children for example learn firstly some sounds then after some time some words and then chunks. After all these processes they eventually begin building simple sentences. Learning a new language is also exactly similar to experiencing baby philosophy. Thus, one needs to consider the time which is going to be allocated besides, students should set achievable targets not being lured by the internet sources.

1.2 Technology

It is common knowledge that technology has facilitated not only the language learning process but also lots of different fields of work. However, there are some downsides of the usage of technology in education if applied improperly. First of all, utilizing MS word software, for example, automatically corrects writers spelling mistakes and this in turn decreases the students’ spelling ability when they write a letter or essays by hand on a sheet of paper. Moreover, watching different videos in a target language is quite effective but students may be disturbed by ads and other suggested videos which are not beneficial for them to learn a language. Besides, online dictionaries are very useful to see the words’ definitions and pronunciation, however, the words that students are seeking may be retained in their short-term memories and easily fade away when they want to use them. In comparison with traditional paper dictionaries students recall the words several times in their minds before finding them in the book. And this subconscious repetition will help them to better memorize and utilize the words in the long run.

Furthermore, most people in third-world countries can not simply afford to own a piece of gadget for their education, so it is hard for them to keep up with the technology. This is why, they learn traditionally. Planning and creating materials in cooperation with technology does not suit them for now. Ultimately, it is better to estimate the merits of cooperating technology in the classroom and set the norms so that learning outcomes will be productive and effective.

1.3 Methodology.

Methodology has evolved significantly and even it has gone so far that we live in post post-method era, meaning there are no best methods that literally work with all types of learners. We must carefully select the materials and methods according to students’ needs. Unfortunately, nowadays most course books are tailored for different purposes. For example, some of them are for business and marketing, and some of them are created for global students. But, one size doesn’t fit all. It means that, one course book can not satisfy any type of learners’ needs. Unfortunately, there are now insufficient amount of published materials on materials development (Tomlinson 1998) and this process is being hinder for inexperienced teachers to ace their teaching skills. This might be the cause that inexperienced teachers may steal students' time and money if they plan the course, materials, and methods inappropriately. For example, the teacher may conduct the lesson using TTT in place of STT. In the traditional style, the level of overall student engagement can be quite low. This may bring about a decline in motivation in students. Motivation and investment in second language acquisition are one of the major factors. Moreover, some of the teachers may structure the lesson without considering several crucial aspects: such as fostering critical and high-order thinking skills, cultural aspects, and types of learners. Every now and then by using CLT method teacher may just reactivate students' background schemata but it may not challenge to further learning. Or implementing the audio lingual method for visual learners could not simply work and it may turn out to be a complete waste of time and money for students. Overall, it is essential to be an expert in language teaching and select materials and methods accordingly. It is advised for amateur teachers to enroll in adequate teacher training programs.

1.4 Rapid change in languages.

English is being influenced by some other outer forces and it is now quickly being changed. To put it another way, celebrities are creating new idioms or jargon that are catching on among natives and confusing foreign learners. Besides, the US has different grammar and accent yet the UK has slightly different grammar and accent. So learners may wonder which one to pick. Moreover, natives are using word constructions-shortening the words and this causes other nonnative learners to misunderstand the gist, especially in listening sections. Learners start picking up some basic grammar and vocabulary of the language until they become fluent in a language, language is also evolving and again causing the learners some anxiety. It would be great if the government of native English countries regulate the standard language usage at least in media coverage.

Conclusion.

Everything that plays a part in human evolution has repercussions; we cannot neglect them. There is now a plethora of challenges in modern-day teaching and if we address the issues by adequately timing and explaining how the language works, incorporating technology in the language learning process with only gaining benefit from it and knowing the materials -what to and how to teach, working constantly on ourselves, keeping up with the recent changes in languages we can overcome those issues in the future.

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